

RESISTANCE, TEMPERATURE AND IRRADIANCE PARAMETER ANALYSIS OF A SINGLE DIODE PHOTOVOLTAIC CELL MODEL

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an analysis of parameter variations of a single-diode solar cell model. The parameters analyzed are the series resistance, shunt resistance, temperature and radiation change. Model equations are derived and simulated. All simulations were performed in Matlab using looping iterative method. Results obtained show that an increase in series resistance causes a decrease in short-circuit current and output power. A decrease in shunt resistance also causes a decrease in short circuit current and output power. An increase in temperature above the nominal value of 25°C causes a significant decrease in the open circuit voltage. An increase in irradiance above a nominal value of 1000 W/m² causes the short circuit current to increase from 8.21A at 1000 W/m² to 10.67A at 1300W/m². It can be seen that parameter variations have a net effect on the current-voltage (I-V) and power-voltage (P – V) characteristics.

KEYWORDS: Series resistance, Shunt resistance, Photovoltaic, Short circuit current, open circuit voltage.

1. INTRODUCTION

Becquerel discovered the photovoltaic effect in electrochemical cells in 1839. However, in 1954, Chapin, Fuller and Pearson developed the first efficient solar cell (Lorenzo, 1994). Since then, similar devices have found its use in providing electricity at remote locations around the world. PV cells contain semiconductors that have a certain band gap (E_g) and thickness. When the photons in the sunlight hit the solar panel, the photons are absorbed by the semiconductor materials. This causes the excited electrons to be knocked off and constitute the generated current. The electrical energy produced by a solar cell at any time instant depends on its intrinsic properties and the incoming solar radiation (Eltawil and Zhao, 2010; Hyeonah and Hyosung, 2013).

To obtain the power-voltage (P-V) and current-voltage (I-V) characterization of a photovoltaic cell, a model of PV cell is required. A general and widespread method is to make use of an electrical equivalent circuit, which is primarily based on a light-generated current source connected in parallel to a p-n junction diode (Vivek and Sawle, 2015). Many models have been proposed for the simulation of a single solar cell for a complete photovoltaic (PV) system at various solar intensities and temperature conditions as seen in (Lorenzo, 1994; Nelson, 2003; Nielson, 1982;

Vivek and Sawle, 2015; Gow and Manning, 1999; Yetayew and Jyothsna 2013; Aurel *et. al.*, 2018; and Andreea *et. al.*, 2017).

Generally, the model of an ideal solar cell consists of a current source in parallel with an ideal diode having saturation current and ideality factor. However, in practice, an ideal solar cell does not exist. Hence, shunt and series resistances are added to the model (Lorenzo, 1994). These are parasitic parameters and are known to produce extrinsic effects (affect the external behavior) on the solar cell model. The curve factors of commercial solar cells are lower than ideal, primarily due to the series resistance (R_s) (Wolf and Rauschenbach, 1963). The resistive losses become larger as substrate size increases. However, in both a laboratory and a production cell, the curve factor is not only limited by R_s but also by low shunt resistance (R_{sh}) (Bowden and Rohatgi, 2001).

Other parameters of a photovoltaic cell are the temperature and irradiance. The effects of variations in diode saturation current and ideality factor were analyzed in extensive details in (Lorenzo, 1994; Nielson, 1982; Rodrigues *et al.*, 2011; Vivek and Sawle, 2015 and Vanjari, 2016). In this

paper, a study of the effects of variations in temperature, a single diode solar cell model is conducted and presented. The objective of this work is to study and understand the

irradiance and parasitic resistances of effects of variations of these parameters in order to improve the performance of a photovoltaic cell.

2. THEORITICAL SINGLE DIODE MODELS

The electronic behavior of a photovoltaic cell is better understood with a circuit model. This model is composed of discrete electrical components. In this section, an ideal

photovoltaic cell model, a single diode model with series resistance and a single diode model with series and shunt resistances are presented.

Figure 1: Ideal single diode model

I_L = Photocurrent

I_D = Diode current

I = Output current

V = Output voltage

From Fig.1, using Kirchoff's current law,

$$I = I_L - I_D \quad (1)$$

The Shockley equation for an ideal diode is given by:

$$I_D = I_0 \left[\exp \frac{qV}{nkT} - 1 \right] \quad (2)$$

q = Electron charge

n = Diode factor

k = Boltzmann constant

T = Operating temperature

I_0 = Diode saturation current

$$\text{Thus, } I = I_L - I_0 \left[\exp \frac{qV}{nkT} - 1 \right] \quad (3)$$

For n_s number of cells,

$$I = I_L - I_0 \left[\exp \frac{qV}{nn_s kT} - 1 \right] \quad (4)$$

The open circuit voltage and short circuit current can be used to characterize a photovoltaic cell.

The short circuit current I_{SC} is obtained when $V = 0$ in equation (4)

$$\text{Thus, } I_{SC} = I = I_L \quad (5)$$

The open circuit voltage V_{OC} is obtained when $I = 0$ in equation (4)

$$I_L = I_0 \left[\exp \frac{qV}{nkT} - 1 \right]$$

$$V_{OC} = \frac{n_s nkT}{q} \ln \left[\frac{I_L}{I_0} + 1 \right] \quad (6)$$

Power

$$P = IV = \left[I_L - I_0 \left[\exp \frac{qV}{nn_s kT} - 1 \right] \right] V \quad (7)$$

As shown in (Nelson, 2003; Nielson, 1982; Rodrigues *et al*, 2011), this ideal model does not provide an accurate representation of a photovoltaic cell. To improve accuracy, parasitic resistances are added to the ideal photovoltaic cell model in fig. 1. First, an equation of the series resistance alone is derived. Then an equation for the combination of series and shunt resistances is derived.

Figure 2: Single diode model with series resistance

R_S = Series resistance

Using similar principles in equations 1 and 2;

$$I_D = I_0 \left[\exp \frac{q(V+IR_S)}{nkT} - 1 \right] \quad (8)$$

For n_s cells;

$$I_D = I_0 \left[\exp \frac{q(V+I n_s R_S)}{n_s n k T} - 1 \right] \quad (10)$$

$$\Rightarrow I = I_L - I_0 \left[\exp \frac{q(V+I n_s R_S)}{n_s n k T} - 1 \right] \quad (11)$$

When $V = 0$;

$$I_{SC} = I_L - I_0 \left[\exp \frac{q I_{SC} R_S}{n_s n k T} - 1 \right] \quad (12)$$

When $I = 0$;

$$I_L = I_0 \left[\exp \frac{q V_{OC}}{n_s n k T} - 1 \right]$$

$$\Rightarrow V_{OC} = \frac{n_s n k T}{q} \ln \left[\frac{I_L}{I_0} + 1 \right] \quad (13)$$

The output power for this model is given by;

$$P = \left[I_L - I_0 \left[\exp \frac{q(V+I n_s R_S)}{n_s n k T} - 1 \right] \right] V \quad (14)$$

Figure 3: Single diode model with series and shunt resistance

R_{SH} = Shunt resistance

Using similar principles in equations (1) and (2);

$$I = I_L - I_D - I_{SH} \quad (15)$$

$$I_{SH} = \frac{V+IR_S}{R_{SH}} \quad (16)$$

$$I = I_L - I_0 \left[\exp \frac{q(V+IR_S)}{nkT} - 1 \right] - \frac{V+IR_S}{R_{SH}} \quad (17)$$

For n_s cells;

$$I = I_L - I_0 \left[\exp \frac{q(V+I n_s R_S)}{n_s n k T} - 1 \right] - \frac{V+I n_s R_S}{n_s R_{SH}} \quad (18)$$

3. SIMULATION MODEL

In this section, the mathematical model used for simulation in Matlab is presented. The simulations were then performed using Matlab looping iterative method. The results are presented in section 4.

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_L &= \frac{G}{G_N} [I_{LN} + K_I(T - T_N)] \\
 I_O &= I_{ON} \left(\frac{T}{T_N}\right)^3 \exp\left[\frac{qE_g}{nk} \left(\frac{1}{T_N} - \frac{1}{T}\right)\right] \\
 I_{ON} &= \frac{I_{SCN}}{\exp\left(\frac{V_{OCN}}{nV_{TN}}\right) - 1} \\
 I &= I_L - I_O \left[\exp\left(\frac{q(V+IR_S)}{nkT}\right) - 1 \right] - \frac{V+IR_S}{R_{SH}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

I_{LN} = Nominal photocurrent
 I_{scn} = Nominal sc current
 V_{ocn} = Nominal oc voltage
 K_v = Temperature voltage constant
 K_i = Temperature current constant
 T = Operating temperature
 T_n = Nominal temperature
 G_n = Nominal irradiance
 E_g = Silicon band gap
 G = Actual irradiance

Table 1: PV cell parameters

Parameters	Values
k	1.38065e-23 J/K
q	1.602e-19 C
Iscn	8.21 A
Vocn	32.9 A
Ki	0.0032 A/K
T	25+273 K (to be varied)
Tn	25+273 K
Gn	1000 W/m ²
n	1.3 (1≤n≤2)
Eg	1.12 J
G	1000 W/m ² (to be varied)
Rs	0.2 Ω (to be varied)
Rsh	415 Ω (to be varied)
I _{LN}	8.21 A

4. RESULTS

A. VARIATION OF SERIES RESISTANCE

Figure 4: Effect of series resistance on the P-V characteristic of a PV cell

Figure 5: Effect of series resistance on the I-V characteristic of a PV cell

B. VARIATION OF SHUNT RESISTANCE

Figure 6: Effect of shunt resistance on the I-V characteristic of a PV cell

Figure 7: Figure 6 expanded

Figure 8: Effect of shunt resistance on the P-V characteristic of a PV cell

Figure 9: Figure 8 expanded

C. VARIATION OF TEMPERATURE

Figure 10: Effect of temperature on the P-V characteristic of a PV cell

Figure 11: Effect of temperature on the I-V characteristic of a PV cell

D. VARIATION OF IRRADIANCE

Figure 12: Effect of irradiance on the P-V characteristic of a PV cell

Figure 13: Effect of irradiance on the I-V characteristic of a PV cell

5. DISCUSSION

In figures 4 and 5, the series resistance was varied from 0 – 0.3Ω with step sizes of 0.05. It can be observed that as the series resistance increases, the I-V curve begins to sag towards the origin. The implication of the sag is a significant decrease in the output voltage. A slight reduction in the short circuit current (I_{sc}) can also be observed from the I-V plot. It can be deduced that very high series resistance values will reduce I_{sc} significantly. At these high values, the series resistance dominates the behavior of the cell making the cell act like a resistor (Nielson, 1982). The P-V characteristic shows an 8.4% drop in maximum power between the 0 and 3Ω series resistance values. Power loss, $P_{loss} = IV_{RS} = I^2 R_S$ increases with an increase in I_o . Hence, losses from series resistances are significant when the illumination intensity is high.

From figure 3, a decrease in shunt resistance results in more current being diverted through R_{sh} for a given voltage. This implies that as the shunt resistance decreases, the I-V curve sags towards the origin as seen in figures 6 and 7. R_{sh} was varied from 100-700Ω with steps of 100. From the plots it can be seen that there was a significant decrease in

6. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the series and shunt resistances have a considerable effect on the output power and voltage with a slight reduction of the short circuit current. This confirms reports in (Priyanka and Ravindra, 2011) and in (Neilson, 1982) that these parasitic parameters have a significant effect on the open circuit voltage and short circuit current

REFERENCES

- Andreea, S., Valentin, M., and Marius, P. (2017). Parameters Extraction for the One-Diode Model of a Solar Cell. *American Institute of Physics Conference Proc.* Pp. 1 – 5. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5017444>
- Aurel, G., Lica, S., Bularka, S., Roland, S. and Dan, Lascu (2018). A Novel High Accuracy PV Cell Model Including Self Heating and Parameter Variation. *Energies*. 11(36): 1-21. doi:10.3390/en11010036
- Bowden S and Rohatgi A (2001). A Rapid accurate determination of series resistance and fill factor losses in industrial silicon solar cells. *Proceedings of 17th European photovoltaic solar energy conference*, pp. 1802–1806.

the short circuit current I_{sc} as R_{sh} decreases. As expected, in figures 8 and 9, output power decreases with a decrease in shunt resistance.

In equation 19, it can be seen that temperature (T) affects I_L , I_o and I . An increase in T, results in an increase in I_L . This is expected since the thermal generated carriers increase with temperature. The exponential terms in I_o and I decrease with an increase in T. The net effect can be seen in figures 10 and 11. An increase in temperature causes a significant decrease in the open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) in both the P-V and I-V plots. The change in V_{oc} is much stronger than the changes in I_{sc} . It can be seen from the P-V plot that it is not advisable to operate a solar cell at temperatures below 25°C.

Figures 12 and 13 show that as irradiance increases, the power also increases. This is expected, however, with significant consequences. The irradiance was varied from 700-1300 W/m² with step sizes of 100. As seen in the I-V plot, as irradiance increases above the nominal irradiance of 1000 W/m², the short circuit current increases drastically from 8.21A at 1000 W/m² to 10.67A at 1300W/m². When the irradiance drops below the nominal value, I_{sc} reduces from 8.21A at 1000 W/m² to 5.75A at 700W/m².

especially for extreme resistance values. Variations in temperature and irradiance have a much stronger effect on the output power, open circuit voltage and short circuit current values. It is recommended that solar cells should not be operated beyond nominal irradiation levels to avoid large short circuit currents.

Eduardo Lorenzo (1994). *Solar Electricity: Engineering of Photovoltaic Systems*. Progensa.

Eltawil, M., and Zhao, Z. (2010). Grid-connected photovoltaic power systems: Technical and potential problems: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. 14(1), 112– 129.

Gow, J.A. and Manning, C.D. (1999). Development of a photovoltaic array model for use in power-electronics simulation studies, *Electric Power Applications, IEE Proceedings* 146(2), 193-200. doi: 10.1049/ip-epa:19990116.

Hyeonah, P. and Hyosung, K. (2013). PV cell modeling on single-diode equivalent circuit, *Industrial Electronics Society, IECON 2013 - 39th Annual Conference of the IEEE*, pp.1845-1849.

Jenny Nelson (2003). *The Physics of Solar Cells*. Imperial College Press.

Nielson, L. D. (1982). Distributed Series Resistance Effects in Solar Cells. *IEEE transactions on Electron Devices*. 29(5):821-827.

Priyanka, S. and Ravindra, N. (2011). Analysis of series and shunt resistance in silicon solar cells using single and double exponential models. *Emerging Materials Research*. 1(1): 33 – 38.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1680/emr.11.00008>

Rodrigues, E. M., Ruli, M., Mendes, V. M. F. and Catalao, J. P. (2011). Simulation of a Solar Cell Considering Single Diode Equivalent Circuit. *REPQ&G* 1(9):1-5 May.

Vanjari, V., Jena, D., and Gaonkar, D. (2016). An Accurate Modeling of Different Types of Photovoltaic Modules Using Experimental Data. *IJ Renewable Energy Research*. 6(3): 970 -974.

Vivek, S. C and Sawle, Y. (2015). Single diode PV cell modeling and study of characteristics of a single and two diode equivalent circuit. *Electrical and Electronics Engineering: An International Journal (ELELIJ)*. 4(3):1-12.

Wolf M and Rauschenbach H (1963). Series resistance effects on solar cell measurements. *Adv. Energy Conv.* 3, 455–479.

Yetayew, T., and Jyothsna, T.R. (2013). Improved single-diode modeling approach for photovoltaic modules using data sheet, *2013 Annual IEEE India Conference (INDICON)*, pp.1-6, doi: 10.1109/INDICON.2013.6726092.